
REGULATORY FRAMEWORK AND PRACTICES OF OPC IN SAUDI ARABIA, UAE AND BAHRAIN: A COMPARATIVE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

One Person Company (OPC) was introduced as a new business vehicle to reduce the bureaucratic procedures involved in establishing a new company. OPC is a company formed by only one person consisting of a sole proprietorship and company business hybrid. It is observed that a great deal of time, money and efficiency were being wasted on bureaucracy matters and inappropriate regulations, hence the reasons why people in Saudi Arabia do invest overseas. It is noted that a foreigner in the UAE and Bahrain can have 100% ownership of a business, and a company can lawfully provide professional services anywhere without limitations. Due to this flexibility and simplicity of the laws of the UAE and Bahrain, this study examines the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's (KSA) New Regulations in order to determine the extent of consistency with the UAE and Bahrain Regulations on OPC. This paper adopts doctrinal legal research as a methodology. The finding reveals that the KSA Regulations are not explicit for the incorporation and operation of OPC. Also, the company laws of Saudi Arabia, UAE and Bahrain are silent on specific issues such as the appointment of a nominee, among others. The silence of the law regarding those issues will likely affect the company's operation, thereby leaving the companies at the mercy of regulations that may be imposed by the Registrar of Companies or other bodies responsible for the company's

regulations. The result further shows that it is easier to run an OPC in Saudi Arabia and UAE than in Bahrain, considering the amount of minimum capital required in Bahrain.

Keywords: Comparative Study; Regulatory Framework; Practices, OPC; Saudi Arabia; UAE; Bahrain

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Previously, a single person cannot incorporate a company in many jurisdictions. The minimum threshold for incorporating a company is 2 persons unless that person could opt for a sole proprietorship. With the development of One Person Company (OPC), a single person is allowed by law to incorporate a company. OPC is a company with separate legal entity, perpetual succession, and limited liability.¹ With the aim to induce entrepreneurs to shift focus from the conventional sole proprietorship form of business to the OPC that will enable them to have access to bank loan, legal protection, etc.² Thus, OPC is believed to bring a great relief for many entrepreneurs, though with clear indication that several aspects of laws guiding limited liability in the country are affected. Although, the development of OPC has changed the regulatory landscape for companies operating in the country in a number of key areas.³

The ease of doing business largely depends on the regulations and legal frameworks governing opening and operating a business. It was argued that in nations like Saudi Arabia, many citizens are forced to invest abroad due to the tight legal framework and bureaucratic procedures.⁴ The deficiency is due to the time commitment and financial costs involved, typically unneeded. Countries like Bahrain and the UAE have created more lenient legal frameworks to make operating a “One Person Company” (OPC) relatively straightforward for potential businesses to reduce these cumbersome bureaucratic procedures. As a result, OPCs have proliferated in the two countries, which have helped their economies. Due to the flexibility and simplicity of the laws of the UAE and Bahrain, it becomes imperative to examine the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia’s (KSA) New Regulations to determine the extent of its consistency with the UAE and Bahrain Regulations on OPC.

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¹ V. Kumar, 'One Person Company: Concept, Issues and Suggestions', (2006) 132 *Corporate Law Adviser*, p 69.

² See S. H. Hammad, & Al-Mehdar, 'Doing business in Saudi Arabia: overview', (2019) 0-520-4520 *Practical Law Country Q&A* p 5; S. M. Al-Sudairi, 'Saudi Arabia Issues New Regulations for Companies, Altering Regulatory Landscape', (2015) *Latham & Watkins Corporate Governance Practice* no. 1911, p 349.

³ W. Hachem, J. El Antoury & C. Burton, *The New Saudi Companies Law and Its Implications for KSA Companies*, Holman Fenwick Willan, Riyadh 2016, <http://www.hfw.com/The-new-Saudi-companies-law-January-2016>.

⁴ R. Wilson, A. Al-Rajhi, A. Al-Salamah & M. Malik, *Economic Development in Saudi Arabia*, Taylors & Francis groups, New York 2004, p 136

Therefore, this paper seeks to compare and contrast the Companies Law of KSA, UAE and the Kingdom of Bahrain relating to the regulatory framework of OPC. In accomplishing this task, this paper evaluates the salient features of OPCs under both laws (Saudi Arabia, UAE and Bahrain), with emphasis on legal entity, succession, restrictions and control of OPC, minimum share capital, nominee, the procedure for the conversion of OPC to other types of company, the role of company's secretary, documents needed for the incorporation as well as the procedure for the incorporation among others.

2.0 BACKGROUND OF OPC IN SAUDI ARABIA

With the introduction of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 in KSA, only one person is required to form OPC (Single Shareholder Limited Liability Company), who can be a shareholder and the director.⁵ The concept of OPC allows professionals to establish their businesses solely. It offers many possibilities and provides a sufficient number of business opportunities to small-scale entrepreneurs who are at an advantage in limiting their liabilities while entering the corporate world. The shareholder may be a natural person or a corporate body. The OPCs are a limited liability in nature. This position means that the company's owner will not be personally liable for the company's debt. The owner may manage the company himself or delegate it to a manager or a board that will do that on his behalf.

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's new Companies Act includes new issues and rules that facilitate commercial regulations and related procedures. It aims to remove all regular and legal bottlenecks to be in tune with emerging trends in the commercial world. One of the new issues from the Companies Act is establishing the Single Shareholder Company, which means it is now possible for one person to establish a limited liability company and shall hold the entire shares, and his liability towards the company's debt is within its capital. This person will have the rights and powers of the General Manager, Board of Directors and Shareholders General Assembly.

Several regulatory bodies regulate the operation and activities of single shareholder companies in Saudi Arabia, some of which are: The Capital Market Authority ("CMA"), established according to the Capital Market Law. The CMA's functions are to regulate

⁵ Article 154(1) of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia)

and develop the Saudi Capital Market by issuing required rules and regulations for implementing the provisions of the Capital Market Law. The primary objectives of the CMA are to create an appropriate investment environment, boost confidence, reinforce transparency and disclosure standards in all listed companies, and protect investors and dealers from illegal acts in the market.⁶ In addition, the Saudi Central Bank (“SAMA”) is the banking, insurance, and financing regulator. SAMA is the national central bank and is a member of the Bank for International Settlements, the Committee for Payments and Market Infrastructures and the Basel Committee for Banking Supervisors.⁷

Another regulatory agency is the Ministry of Investment of Saudi Arabia (MISA) is responsible for following up and assessing investment performance, alleviating the difficulties encountered by investors, conducting studies and research and drafting executive plans to stimulate local investments.⁸ The Ministry of Commerce is responsible for developing and implementing policies and mechanisms that govern the commerce and investment sectors. Apart from issuing a Chamber of Commerce Certificate, COC facilitates the attestation of formal company letters, which is mandatory in official communication. As part of its process, COC will register the General Manager’s signature (including any authorised signatories) to be able to attest future documents.⁹ The subsequent heading identifies some of the features of OPC under KSA law.

3.0 BACKGROUND OF OPC IN UAE

The Simple Commandite Company, a type of OPC used in the UAE, has been legally recognised in Articles 9 and 69 of the UAE Commercial Companies Law. The structure comprises a limited partner and an active partner who manages the business. The active partner is liable personally and jointly for the company’s liabilities, while the limited partner shall not be liable to the liable to for the company’s liabilities save to the extent of their investment in the company.

The central monarchical and regional governments, called emirates, govern the regulatory framework for establishing businesses in the UAE. At the central level, the

⁶ (<https://www.saudiexchange.sa/wps/portal/tadawul/knowledge-center/about/Capital-Market-Overview?locale>)

⁷ (<https://www.saudiexchange.sa/wps/portal/tadawul/knowledge-center/about/Capital-Market-Overview?locale>)

⁸ (<https://transcendyourbusiness.com/setup-your-company-in-saudi-arabia/>)

⁹ (<https://transcendyourbusiness.com/setup-your-company-in-saudi-arabia/>)

principal act governing Companies' operation is the UAE Commercial Companies Law (Federal Law No. 2 of 2015). The law identifies company requirements regarding shareholders, directors, minimum capital levels and incorporation procedures. Notably, it also sets the different types of businesses and how their license can be acquired. Consequently, the licence and the institution that would grant it depend on the region and the type of company one wishes to operate – whether a Joint Liability Company, Simple Commandite Company (also known as the OPC),¹⁰ Limited Liability Company, Public Joint Stock Company or Private Joint Stock Company.

4.0 BAHRAIN'S OPC REGULATORY FRAMEWORK

The operations of OPC in Bahrain, including its registration, activities and types, are regulated by the Commercial Companies Law of 2001, later amended by law No. 50 of 2014 and Law 28 of 2015 (Revised Law). Bahrain's Single Person Company carries the literal definition of One Person Company because one person can only run it. It is similar to a sole proprietorship except that in SPC, founders or directors can only be liable to the extent of the company's capital for any damage suffered by the company, its partners or shareholders. Owing to its simplicity, SPC is the fastest growing type of company in Bahrain today. Moreover, it can be operated by both natural and Juristic, whether foreign or indigenous.

4.1 IDENTIFICATION OF SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES

The identification, examination and analysis of the similarities and differences in the operation of OPC in Saudi, UAE and Bahrain will foster understanding of this concept of discussion.

4.2 DISCUSSION BASED ON CERTAIN FEATURES

OPCs have unique features from other companies. These features expose the beauty of OPC. In this discussion, the researcher presents the position of Saudi, UAE and Bahrain Company Laws regarding each feature highlighted below.

i. ROLE OF OPC SECRETARIES

a. Saudi

A business secretary or a director may sign OPC's annual return. This authority raises a question about the function of company secretaries inside OPC. OPC has a limited

¹⁰ Single Person Company (OPC) refers to a Single Commandite Company under the UAE Laws. For the purpose of this study OPC will be used instead.

structure due to its small annual turnover. A company secretary cannot work full time in this constrained structure. However, by offering business advice and aid in the company's management, a company secretary can contribute positively to OPC.¹¹

b. UAE

The position of Company Secretaries of OPC was not categorically defined in the UAE's Companies Law. Therefore, the only requirement is for the manager or the Board of Directors to call the company General Assembly at least once every year. The meeting must be within the four months that follow the conclusion of the firm's fiscal year. The General Assembly shall be called to order at the time and location specified in the invitation letter.¹²

According to the roles in the aforementioned legal provision, it is tempting to assume that the manager meant by the law is the secretary because, in many jurisdictions, a company secretary's overall responsibilities include giving notice of meetings, which typically includes giving the date, time, and location of the meeting among other things. However, a close examination of OPCs' constrained structures indicates that they cannot support a company secretary in a full-time position, which is why the law is silent on secretaries' responsibilities.

c. Bahrain

The Bahraini Companies Law is equally quiet regarding the function of Bahrain's Single Person Company Secretaries. Similar to the UAE's rules, the legislation mandates that the general assembly meet at least once every year, during the first four months after the end of the company's fiscal year, at the managers' call.¹³ The wisdom of this provision can also be tied to the fact that single-person companies have a limited financial capacity and cannot afford to keep a company secretary employed full-time.

ii. PROCEDURAL FORMALITIES REGARDING UNWRITTEN CONTRACTS

a. Saudi

¹¹ V. Balachandran & S. Putty, 'An Overview of the Law and Practice Pertaining to One Person

Company (OPC) Under the Companies Act, 2013', 2014 *Chartered Secretary*, p. 27.

¹² Article 92 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

¹³ Article 283(b) of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

According to the law, when an OPC enters into an unwritten agreement, the agreement's terms must either be stated in the company's memorandum or noted in the minutes of the board meeting that followed the unwritten agreement.¹⁴

b. UAE

The law does not address the legality of unwritten contracts. Therefore, an individual working with an OPC could be left to enter an unwritten contract at his own risk.

c. Bahrain

The Bahrain Companies Law also lacks any rules or formalities governing oral agreements. Therefore, a person dealing with a Single Person Company must be careful about any unwritten contracts.

iii. LIAISON WITH THE REGISTRAR OF OPC AND GENERAL PUBLIC

a. Saudi

OPC may only have one director who is also a single shareholder. When dealing with public inquiries or inquiries from registrars of companies, the situation can undoubtedly be problematic if this director is not physically present in the company to handle difficulties. Other types of corporations have two or more directors, one of whom is the managing director and both of whom are ready to answer questions from members of the public or the Registrar of companies.¹⁵

b. UAE

General Public members have little trouble contacting the company with questions, and the corporation promptly responds to inquiries from the Registrar of Companies at all pertinent periods. This access is valid because the law permits the addition of one or more additional directors to an OPC in addition to the original director. These additional directors will always be accessible to respond to inquiries about the company from the public or the Registrar of Companies.

c. Bahrain

The legislation allows a Single Person Company to be managed by just one director, the single owner. However, when this director is absent, the law permits the appointment

¹⁴ Article 162 of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia)

¹⁵ T. Ramappa, 'Why A One Person Company', 2014 *Chartered Secretary*, p 30.

of one or more directors who will always be ready to answer questions from public members or the company registrar.¹⁶

iv. APPOINTMENT OF A NOMINEE

a. Saudi

The New Professional Companies Law, 2020, is quiet on the topic of a nominee who would take over as sole owner in the event of the owner's passing.

b. UAE

The appointment of a nominee who should take over the firm's operation in the case of the sole owner's death is not covered by UAE company law; however, additional individuals, either natural or corporate persons, may be designated as silent partners. Silent partners are not responsible for the company's debts beyond the number of their respective capital shares.

c. Bahrain

There is no provision regarding the designation of a Nominee who should assume business control if the single owner passes away. However, the owner may nominate or appoint one or more managers to represent the company before the courts and other parties.

v. POSITION ON DUAL MEMBERSHIP OF OPC

a. Saudi

According to Saudi law, a natural person can only establish or possess one limited liability corporation at a time. No one person, natural or legal, limited liability company may establish or acquire ownership of another one-person, limited liability corporation.¹⁷

b. UAE

The question of whether a person can belong to two or more OPCs is left unanswered by the legislation.

c. Bahrain

Bahrain's companies' law is equally silent about dual membership of Single Person Companies.

vi. TURNOVER LIMIT

¹⁶ T. Ramappa, 'Why A One Person Company', p. 31.

¹⁷ Article 154(2) of the New Professional Company Law of KSA, 2020

a. Saudi

In Saudi law, there is a relatively low turnover threshold. According to the law, 10% of the company's net profit must go toward setting up a statutory reserve.¹⁸

b. UAE

The position of the law regarding the turnover cap is not covered by the law governing corporations.

c. Bahrain

Unless the articles of organization stipulate a more significant proportion, a statutory (legal) reserve of 10% of net income is set aside annually. If the reserve equals 50% of the paid-up capital or less, this deduction may be deferred, provided an organization's articles specify a more significant percentage. However, the deduction must resume if the statutory reserve drops below the specified percentage and must continue until the reserve reaches the specified percentage. In years when the company's profits do not guarantee such a restriction, the statutory reserve may be utilized to assure the payout of dividends to the shareholders not exceeding 5% of the paid-up capital.¹⁹

vii. CONVERSION OF OPC TO OTHER TYPES OF COMPANY AND VICE VERSA

The change in the company's formation is included in the conversion of OPC into another entity. Usually, conversion is required when a business needs to be modified or can no longer run in its original form owing to specific factors.

a. Conversion of OPC under Saudi Law

The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia's New Professional Companies Law, 2020 does not outline a specific process or provision for converting an OPC into a public company or a public company into a public company. The law states, however, that a company may be transformed into a different type of company under a decision issued following the conditions prescribed for the amendment of the company's articles of association or incorporation, so long as it satisfies the requirements of incorporation, publication, and registration in the commercial register prescribed for the type the company transformed.²⁰

b. Conversion under the UAE

¹⁸ Article 176 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

¹⁹ Article 224 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

²⁰ Article 187 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

Per the provisions of the Law and the Regulations and Decisions governing the conversion of companies as issued by the Ministry of Economy or the Securities & Commodities Authority, the Commercial Companies Law guarantees the conversion of an OPC to a Limited Liability Company or Joint Stock Company while maintaining its legal personality. When specific requirements are completed, conversions from OPC or other forms of corporations are made.

These include:

- (a) Issuing a Decision following the applicable conditions to amend the Memorandum of Association and the Articles of Association of the company.
- (b) The expiry of a period of at least two audited financial years of the company from the date of its registration in the Commercial Register.
- (c) The partners' unanimous consent in the event of conversion into a Joint Liability Company.
- (d) Completing the applicable incorporation and registration procedures to the proposed conversion form.²¹

In addition to meeting the requirements mentioned above, a company considering a conversion must notify the Ministry of Economy or the Securities and Commodities Authority of its intention. The application must be supported with a statement of the company's assets, rights, and obligations. Other documents include an assessment of the value, a statement of the objections or the expiration of their terms. The conversion decision of an OPC or any other Company must be submitted to and authorized by the Securities and Commodities Authority or the Ministry of Economy before the new company can be incorporated in the Register of Companies.²²

c. Conversion under the Bahrain Companies Law

If a limited liability business has fewer than two partners, it must change its legal status to a single-person company. For example, a Limited Liability Company may have up to fifty (50) shareholders. The company must convert into a single-person business if only one person holds the whole company's shares. The exception is when the shareholders are added within thirty days.²³

²¹ Article 274 of the Commercial Companies Law, 2015 – United Arab Emirate

²² Article 282 of the Commercial Companies Law, 2015 – United Arab Emirate

²³ Article 261 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

viii. RESTRICTIONS AND CONTROLS OF OPC

a. Saudi

According to Article 154 of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia), the OPC must abide by rules that apply to private businesses, including:

1. OPC (Limited Liability Company) is not permitted to do any banking, finance, saving, or insurance business or to invest money on behalf of third parties.²⁴
2. A limited liability company controlled by one individual, whether natural or legal, is not permitted to create or acquire another individual's limited liability company.²⁵
3. The articles of incorporation must be published at the company's expense on the Ministry's website within 30 days of the date of incorporation by the company's directors. In addition, the directors must register the firm with the commercial registry within that time.²⁶
4. A limited liability company shall have one or more auditors²⁷
5. The company's directors shall prepare, for each fiscal year, the company's financial statements.²⁸

b. UAE

An OPC under UAE's Law must adhere to the following rules in order to function effectively:

1. Before beginning its activity, the company must obtain all approvals and licenses necessary for the activity that the company will conduct in the State.
2. The company must start its primary operations in the UAE after it has been formed there; unless otherwise permitted by its memorandum of association, it is not permitted to conduct business outside the UAE.
3. The company is prohibited from engaging in banking or insurance activities as only public joint stock companies may do so.²⁹

²⁴ Article 153 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

²⁵ Article 154(2) of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

²⁶ Article 158 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

²⁷ Article 166 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

²⁸ Article 175 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

²⁹ Article 11 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

4. The company cannot be registered under a name already registered in the UAE or any confusingly similar name.³⁰
5. Every contract, document, communication, and application form issued by the company must include the company's name, legal form, registration number, and address. In addition, if the company's share capital is added to these details, the amount of the paid share capital must also be indicated.³¹
6. A company's memorandum of association and amendments must be written in Arabic and certified by a notary public. However, if the memorandum is also published in another language besides Arabic, the Arabic version will take precedence in the United Arab Emirates.³²
7. The Memorandum of Association of the Company and any amendments must be registered with the appropriate authority in the Commercial Register to be valid.³³
8. The company must keep accounting records of its activities to accurately display its financial situation at any moment and allow partners or shareholders to verify that its books are being kept in line with the law.³⁴
9. The right of the creditors to recover debt from the sole partner or sponsor where either of them served as a grantor.³⁵

c. Bahrain

Before a Single Person Company may be appropriately registered and granted a business license, it must adhere to some rules. These include:

1. The words "Single Person Company" or SPC must appear after the company name and be connected to the owner's identity.³⁶
2. A Notary Public must certify that the Company's Memorandum of Association is drafted in Arabic and legally binding.³⁷

³⁰ Article 12 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

³¹ Article 13 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

³² Article 14 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

³³ Article 15 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

³⁴ Article 26 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

³⁵ H. A. S. Al Nasser, M. I. Negasi, Wan Mohd Zulhafiz Bin Wan Zahari, 'Creditors' Guarantees of a One-Person Limited Liability Company in the Omani and UAE Companies Law and Ways to Protect Them', (2022) Vol. VIII, Issue 23 *International E-Journal of Advances in Social Sciences*, p 534.

³⁶ Article 291 of the Companies Law of Bahrain

³⁷ Article 6 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

3. The company must abide by the rules prohibiting it from conducting banking, insurance, and fund investing for third parties.³⁸
4. The company must maintain a register of members.³⁹

ix. SUCCESSION

a. Saudi

Unless the firm's articles of incorporation specifically mention otherwise, a limited liability company is not terminated by a partner's death, interdiction, declaration of bankruptcy, insolvency, or withdrawal.⁴⁰

b. UAE

According to the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirates, an OPC may be dissolved for any reason, including the death, bankruptcy, insolvency, or loss of legal capacity of any partner, the withdrawal of the sole acting partner, the continuation of a Joint Liability Company with a single partner for six months, and the failure of the company to modify its legal status during that time.⁴¹

However, if the remaining partners agree unanimously to continue and succeed the deceased partner, the death, bankruptcy, insolvency, or reduction in the number of partners of the company may be resolved.⁴²

d. Bahrain

Generally, the Single Person Company dissolves upon the owner's death and may also dissolve upon the dissolution of the corporate person owning its capital. However, the company's owner can succeed if the heirs decide to carry on with business operations in any other legal form within six months following the owner's passing.⁴³

x. MINIMUM SHARE CAPITAL

a. Saudi

Saudi legislation does not specify the minimum share capital required to create an OPC or limited liability company. However, the legislation specifies that one person may form a limited liability company and that all of the firm's shares may revert to that

³⁸ Article 262 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

³⁹ Article 171 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁴⁰ Article 179 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁴¹ Article 296 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁴² Article 297 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁴³ Article 295 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

person, as the minimal number of individuals required to establish a limited liability company.⁴⁴

b. UAE

Although there is no minimum share capital required by UAE legislation, the company must have enough money to fulfill the objectives of its incorporation. However, the UAE Companies Law stipulates that at least one or more joint partners who are accountable, severally, and jointly must own the company to establish an OPC.

c. Bahrain

The minimum requirements for setting up an OPC include:

(i) The minimum capital shall not be less than twenty thousand Bahraini dinars.⁴⁵

(ii) One natural or corporate person must fully own the capital of the company.⁴⁶

xi. FILING DOCUMENTS WITH THE REGISTRAR OF THE COMPANY

a. Saudi

Companies that have been legally registered and acknowledged are listed in the Registrar of Companies' records. The Company's Memorandum and Articles of Incorporation are only two examples of the paperwork that must be submitted to the Registrar of Companies. Accordingly, the legislation requires the company's directors to publish the articles of incorporation at the company's expense on the Ministry's website within 30 days after the date of incorporation and to register the company with the commercial register within that same time frame.⁴⁷

b. UAE

Similar to the Law in Saudi, a Company's Memorandum of Association and any amendments to that is vital. According to the law, for them to be effective, they must be registered in the Commercial Register with the appropriate authorities.⁴⁸ Where the memorandum is defective, the legality of the company's operation is threatened.

c. Bahrain

The provision of the Bahrain law is similar to those mentioned above. In addition, the memorandum must be notarized in the Commercial Registry and published in the

⁴⁴ Article 154 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁴⁵ Article 293 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁴⁶ Article 289 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁴⁷ Article 158 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁴⁸ Article 15 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

Official Gazette at the company's expense.⁴⁹ Without registering and publishing the company's Memorandum of Association and subsequent amendments, the Memorandum of Association shall not take effect on third parties.⁵⁰

xii. PROCEDURE ON THE PROCESS OF INCORPORATION

a. Saudi

The procedure of Incorporation of OPC in Saudi is left in the hands of regulatory bodies like the Ministry of Commerce and Industry because the principal is silent on the issue.

b. UAE

The United Arab Emirates OPC's incorporation process is identical to that of a joint liability company, which is formed in the following ways:⁵¹

1. Obtain a form for the formation application from the local agency with jurisdiction over companies' business in the appropriate Emirate.
2. Send the appropriate authority the incorporation application and the paperwork needed for the license and registration processes.
3. The applicant is then required by the competent authority to produce the required statements and papers or to change the company's memorandum of association to comply with the requirements of this Law and the Decisions issued thereunder.
4. Following completion of the statements and papers or making the necessary adjustments, the competent body must decide on the application for business incorporation within 5 (five) working days at the latest. If the application is denied, the denial must be explained.
5. The applicant may complain within 15 (fifteen) working days with the General Manager of the competent authority or his representative if the competent authority rejects the application or the time frame specified in clause 4 of this Article expires without a decision on the application. The applicant may file an appeal to the appropriate Court within 30 (thirty) days after notification of the rejection or the expiration of the preceding time, as applicable. Provided the

⁴⁹ Article 30 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁵⁰ Article 7 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁵¹ Article 43 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

grievance is rejected or not resolved within 15 working days of the date on which it was filed.

6. The competent Court must register the firm in the Commercial Register and grant a trade license if the application for incorporation is approved.
7. The company must give a copy of the trade license and the firm's Memorandum of Association to the Registrar within 5 (five) working days of the trade license's issuance date so that they can be published following the rules set forth by the Minister in this regard.⁵²

c. Bahrain

The procedure for the incorporation of a Single Person Company in Bahrain is as follows:

1. The applicant must choose a company name that is distinct from the names of any Bahraini legal entities. The final letters of the company name must be "Single Person Company" or the abbreviation "SPC".
2. An application form must be submitted to the Ministry of Industry, Commerce and Tourism with all relevant personal and professional information (MOICT). In addition, the application must include the SPC's shares, paid-up capital, and the owner's qualifications.
3. Articles of Incorporation: This is an SPC's primary document because it contains the company's rules. The notary public must sign the document when it has been completed and approved by the Ministry, and a copy must be made.
4. Commercial Registration: In order to obtain the commercial registration, a person must also meet the following requirements in addition to fulfilling the activity and ownership requirements: be at least 18 years old (some commercial activities call for a minimum age of 21), be of sound mind, be committed to their business (those who are currently employed in the private sector must present a "No Objection" certificate from their current employer), and be free of any criminal records.
5. Final Approval: It may take up to two weeks for the application to be reviewed thoroughly, and once approved, the business can operate after the Articles of

⁵² Article 43 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

Association, and all other supporting documents are submitted to the MOICT for SPC registration.

xiii. REQUIRED DOCUMENTS FOR INCORPORATION OF OPC

a. Saudi

The Saudi Companies Law does not explicitly mention the documentation needed to incorporate OPC; hence it is left in the hands of regulatory bodies like the Ministry of Commerce and Industry.

b. UAE

Various documents are required to be submitted to the DED, which include:

1. Application form for reservation of the trade name of the company
2. Application form for initial license approval
3. The board resolutions
4. The draft copy of the Memorandum and Articles of Association
5. Corporate documents of the corporate shareholder include passport copies of the individual shareholders and the officers (directors/manager and general manager).⁵³

c. Bahrain

The documents needed for the incorporation of OPC in Bahrain require the following:

1. Application form of registering the company
2. A draft copy of the Memorandum and Articles of Association
3. Capital Deposit Certificate (after pre-approval)
4. Appointment letter from an external auditor
5. Copy of Bahraini ID of the investor and the director
6. Copy of company's Commercial Registration
7. Board of Directors resolution for the establishment of SPC
8. Copy of the applicant's educational qualifications
9. Proposed commercial address under which the business is going to operate⁵⁴

xiv. MEMORANDUM OF ASSOCIATION

a. Memorandum of Association of Saudi

⁵³<https://www.dlapiperintelligence.com/goingglobal/corporate/index.html?t=06-incorporation-process&c=AE>

⁵⁴ <https://www.google.com/amp/s/www.businesssetup.com/bh/single-person-company-spc-bahrain%3famp>

The memorandum outlines the fundamental requirements that must be met before a company can be incorporated; these requirements were added to benefit the shareholders, creditors, and the general public. According to Article 156 of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 of KSA, the Memorandum of Association must take the form specified by Saudi Companies Law.

b. Memorandum of Association of UAE

One of a company's most crucial papers is its memorandum of association. The Memorandum of Association and any amendments must be written in Arabic and attested by a Notary Public per the UAE's Companies Law; otherwise, the Memorandum of Association or the change to that will be deemed illegal. However, Arabic will be used in the UAE if the Memorandum of Association is written in another language.⁵⁵

According to the UAE's Companies Law, an OPC must abide by the joint liability company's memorandum of association's regulations. As a result, the following provisions from the joint liability company's memorandum of association apply to OPC:

1. The full name of each partner, his nationality, date of birth and domicile;
2. The name, address and trade name, if any, of the company and the objective for which it was established;
3. The head office of the company and its branches, if any;
4. The capital of the company and the shares of every partner and the estimated value of such shares, how they are assessed and the date of their falling due;
5. The commencement date of the company and the date of termination, if applicable;
6. The method by which the company is to be managed, with particulars of the names of those persons who may sign on behalf of the company and the extent of their authority;
7. The commencement date and the expiry date of the financial year;
8. The rate of distributing profits and losses.
9. The conditions of assignment of shares in the company, if any.⁵⁶

In addition, the names of the Joint Partners and the Silent Partners must also be included in the Memorandum of Association of an OPC. The company shall be presumed

⁵⁵ Article 14 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

⁵⁶ Article 42 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

to be a Joint Liability Company, and all partners shall be deemed Joint Partners if such partners are not explicitly stated in the Memorandum of Association.⁵⁷

c. Bahrain

The Memorandum of Association and its amendments for corporations in Bahrain, excluding associations in partnerships, must be written in Arabic and legalized by a Notary Public. Otherwise, the Memorandum of Association and any amendments become void.⁵⁸

The Bahrain Companies Law is clear that Single Person Companies must abide by the same regulations as Bahrain's Limited Liability Companies. So, per Bahraini company legislation, a single-person company's memorandum of association must contain the following:

1. The names, titles and nationalities of partners.
2. The company's headquarters.
3. The company's name and address, with the addition of the phrase (a limited liability Company).
4. The company's objectives.
5. Each partner provides the company's capital and the cash and in-kind shares with a detailed description of the kind shares and their value.
6. The conditions of shares assignment.
7. The term of the company, if any
8. The names of those entrusted with the company's management from among the partners or others, and the names of the control board members in case the law stipulate such board's existence.
9. Distribution methods of profits and losses⁵⁹

The company's memorandum of association may also contain special clauses governing the right of retrieval of partners' shares and the methods used to value those shares when this right is exercised, the formation of reserves other than the statutory reserve, the organization of the company's finances and accounts, and the reasons for

⁵⁷ Article 65 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

⁵⁸ Article 6 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁵⁹ Article 265 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

the dissolution of the company. The Minister of Commerce and Industry may also order the inclusion of additional information not mentioned above.⁶⁰

4.3 SIMILARITIES

The companies' laws applicable to the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates and the Kingdom of Bahrain have some similarities regarding the legal entity, succession, restrictions and procedure for incorporation.

i. SUCCESSION

The Saudi Companies Law provides for succession on the death or bankruptcy of the owner.⁶¹ The Companies Law of UAE is equally explicit that a OPC may be dissolved by any reason of death, bankruptcy or insolvency of any of the company's partners or his loss of legal capacity.⁶² However, the company may continue to operate if the other partners unanimously agree to continue and succeed the fallen partner.⁶³ This position is very similar to the position in Bahrain because the law is that Single Person Company terminates upon the owner's death and can also be terminated on the termination of the corporate person owning its capital. However, the company's owner can be succeeded if the heirs choose to continue the company in any other legal form within six months at most from the owner's death.⁶⁴

ii. RESTRICTIONS AND PENALTY FOR NON-COMPLIANCE

Under Saudi law, compliance is strict. Therefore, any limited liability company or OPC incorporated in violation of Articles 153, 154, 156 and 157 of the law, such as engaging in banking, financing, saving or insurance activities, or investment of funds for third parties,⁶⁵ setting up or owning another limited liability company of one person besides an existing one⁶⁶, not having an auditor⁶⁷ and not preparing for each fiscal year, the company's financial statements⁶⁸ shall be considered null and void vis-a-vis any stakeholder.⁶⁹

⁶⁰ Article 265(b)&(c) of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁶¹ Article 179 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁶² Article 296 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁶³ Article 297 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁶⁴ Article 295 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁶⁵ Article 153 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁶⁶ Article 154(2) of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁶⁷ Article 166 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁶⁸ Article 175 of the New Professional Companies Law of KSA, 2020

⁶⁹ Article 159 of the New Companies Law of KSA, 2020

In the United Arab Emirates, for an OPC to have an effective operation, it must comply with specific regulations such as obtaining all the approvals and licences as required for the activity to be conducted by the company in the State. After successfully incorporating the company, it must commence its main activities inside the UAE. The company cannot conduct banking and insurance activities as such businesses may only be conducted by Public Joint Stock Companies.⁷⁰ The company must not be registered in a name previously registered in the UAE or in any similar name to the extent that it may lead to confusion⁷¹ The Memorandum of Association of a company and each amendment to it shall be made in Arabic and attested by the Notary Public. If the memorandum is issued in a foreign language besides Arabic, the Arabic version will prevail in the UAE.⁷² The Company's Memorandum of Association and any amendment to it must be registered in the Commercial Register with the competent authority to be effective.⁷³

There is also the requirement for compliance that the company must maintain accounting records showing its transactions to accurately reveal at any time the financial position of the company and enable the partners or shareholders to confirm that the accounts of the company are correctly kept under the provisions of the law⁷⁴

On the other hand, Bahrain company law requires similar compliance from operators of Single Person Companies such that the Memorandum of Association of the Company must be written in Arabic and legalised by a Notary Public.⁷⁵ The company must comply with the regulations restricting it from carrying out the business of insurance, Banking and fund investment for third parties.⁷⁶ The company must maintain a register of members.⁷⁷

iii. APPOINTMENT OF A NOMINEE

Saudi, UAE and Bahrain are silent on the appointment of a Nominee. If the sole owner dies, the nominee shall take his place. Unlike India, the United States, Malaysia, Algeria, Argentina, Brazil, Papua New Guinea, and Fiji, Germany have a provision that provides

⁷⁰ Article 11 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁷¹ Article 12 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁷² Article 14 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁷³ Article 15 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁷⁴ Article 26 of the Companies Law of UAE, 2015

⁷⁵ Article 6 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁷⁶ Article 262 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁷⁷ Article 171 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

for the appointment of a nominee director or shareholder to replace the single owner in cases of eventualities. This permission is although he is not considered a member or officer of the company for whatever reason except in the absence of the sole shareholder, where he died or became incapacitated. However, the nominee must give his consent, and such consent can be withdrawn by the nominee whenever he wishes. The above finding is consistent with the finding of the study of Abdul-Jabbar where he found that an OPC in UAE can be terminated at the expiration of the period contained in the certificated issued to OPC⁷⁸ and the law does not contemplate the appointment of a Nominee as it happens in order jurisdiction like India.

iv. LEGAL ENTITY

In Saudi, UAE and Bahrain, OPC has a separate legal personality from its owner (shareholder) and the liability of the shareholder is limited to the amount unpaid.

v. MEMORANDUM OF ASSOCIATION

In Saudi, UAE and Bahrain, the Memorandum of Association of a company is one of the most important documents of a company. Therefore, the UAE's law added that the Memorandum of Association and each amendment must be made in Arabic and attested by the Notary Public. The failure will cause the Memorandum of Association or its amendment to be invalid. Nevertheless, if the Memorandum of Association is written in a foreign language in addition to Arabic, it is the Arabic text that will be applicable in the UAE.⁷⁹

4.4 DIFFERENCES

There are slight differences between the operation of OPC in Saudi Arabia, UAE and Bahrain. These differences are discussed below.

i. MINIMUM SHARE CAPITAL

The Saudi Companies Law is silent regarding the minimum shares required to set up an OPC. UAE Companies law also did not prescribe any minimum share capital but the striking difference with Saudi is that UAE law demands that a company have adequate capital to achieve the purpose of its incorporation.⁸⁰ At the same time, the Bahrain

⁷⁸ Zein Ghanem Abdul-Jabbar (2018). The Risk of Allocating a Financial Liability in a One Person Company a Comparative Study. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume 56, Issue 4, pp. 391-402 at 402.

⁷⁹ Article 14 of the Companies Law of the United Arab Emirate, 2015

⁸⁰<https://www.dlapiperintelligence.com/goingglobal/corporate/index.html?t=06-incorporation-process&c=AE>

Companies Law states that the minimum requirement for setting up an OPC is that the minimum capital shall not be less than twenty thousand Bahraini dinars.⁸¹

Abdul-Jabbar having found that the UAE law did not prescribe any minimum share capital, recommended in his study that authorities concerned in the Ministry of Economy should provide a certain amount as a minimum share capital before a person can incorporate an OPC in UAE and further suggested that it should not be below three Million Dirhams so as to give confidence to the creditors in the event an OPC is unable to settle its debt.⁸²

ii. ROLE OF COMPANIES' SECRETARY

Under Saudi law, a company secretary offers a productive role in OPC by providing business consultancy and assistance in the company's management.⁸³ While in both UAE and Bahrain, the laws do not expressly mention a secretary's office, much less his/her duties.

iii. PROCEDURAL FORMALITIES REGARDING UNWRITTEN CONTRACTS

The Saudi New Professional Companies law provides that where an OPC enters into an unwritten contract, the terms of the contract must either be contained in the company's memorandum or should be recorded in the minute book of the board meeting after such an unwritten contract.⁸⁴ However, the UAE and Bahrain's Companies Law are silent on regulations/formalities of unwritten contracts.

iv. LIAISON WITH THE REGISTRAR OF OPC AND GENERAL PUBLIC

In Saudi, the New Professional Companies Law provides for one director who is not available in the company to handle issues, and the situation can indeed cause a problem when OPC has to deal with public queries or queries from the Registrar of companies. However, UAE and Bahrain have no such problems or difficulties. This flexibility is because the laws of UAE and Bahrain allow for the addition of one or more directors who will always be available to take up queries against the company from the general public or the Registrar of Companies. Therefore, the members of the General Public

⁸¹ Article 293 of the Companies Law of Bahrain, 2001

⁸² Zein Ghanem Abdul-Jabbar (2018). The Risk of Allocating a Financial Liability in a One Person Company a Comparative Study. *European Journal of Social Sciences*, Volume 56, Issue 4, pp. 391-402 at 401.

⁸³ Balachandran V. and Sudheendra Putty, "An Overview of the Law and Practice Pertaining to One Person

Company (OPC) Under the Companies Act, 2013", Chartered Secretary, August 2014, pp. 23-27, at p. 27

⁸⁴ Article 162 of the New Professional Companies Law, 2020 (Kingdom of Saudi Arabia)

face no difficulty in sending in queries to the company or the company attending to queries from the Registrar of Companies at all material times.

v. POSITION ON DUAL MEMBERSHIP OF OPC

The laws of UAE and Bahrain are silent as to whether a person can be a member of two or more OPC. This situation is unlike in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, where a natural person may not set up or own more than one limited liability Company of one person, and a limited liability company owned by one person, natural or legal, may not set up or own another limited liability company of one person.⁸⁵

vi. CONVERSION OF OPC TO OTHER COMPANY AND VICE VERSA

The New Professional Companies Law, 2020 of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia has not provided a detailed procedure or provision for converting OPC to a public company or public company to OPC. In comparison, UAE and Bahrain company laws have provided a detailed procedure for converting OPC to other types of companies.

vii. PROCEDURE ON THE PROCESS OF INCORPORATION AND REQUIRED DOCUMENTS FOR INCORPORATION OF OPC

The Saudi Companies Law did not specifically mention about the procedure and documents needed for incorporation of OPC. On the other hand, UAE and Bahrain laws have provided the procedure and the documents needed to incorporate OPC. The table below illustrates the discussions canvassed above.

⁸⁵ Article 154(2) of the New Professional Company Law of KSA, 2020

TABLE 1: SILENT FEATURES OF OPC

COUNTRY	SHARE CAPITAL	COMPANY'S SECRETARY	PROCEDURAL FORMALITIES ON UNWRITTEN CONTRACTS	RELATIONS WITH REGISTRAR	DUAL MEMBERSHIP	CONVERSION	PROCEDURE OF INCORPORATION
KSA	Silent	Offers a Productive Role	Regulations are provided	Having difficulties	Considered	Absence of Procedure	Not Specified
BAHRAIN	Specified	Not Recognised	Silent	Absence of Challenge	Silent	Procedure is provided	Specified
UAE	Specified/requires adequate capital	Not Recognised	Silent	Absence of Challenge	Silent	Procedure is provided	Specified

5.0 CONCLUSION

It follows from the above discussion that OPCs in the three countries share certain similarities, especially in areas like a succession of the company, limited liability, penalty for non-compliance, the appointment of a nominee, and documentation, among others. These similarities have made businesses easier compared to countries whose legal framework does not have similar features. However, in a few other cases, all the countries were silent on issues like nominee appointments. This silence has created a lacuna for either the business owner to act based on discretion or the Registrar of Companies to devise regulations that will address that.

The differences between the three countries have, at some point, put the countries at a disadvantage compared to others. Bahrain's imposition of a minimum capital share of 20,000 dinars will compel businesses to run without registration. Saudi Arabia's restriction on OPC proprietors of OPCs not to set up another OPC may be inferred as one of the reasons why the growth of businesses is passive compared to in UAE and Bahrain. As such, UAE offers the most favourable rule hence why in the Emirates today, a company can be opened from scratch in a day.